

Molybdenum Complexes of Bioinorganic Interest : Studies on the Bonding Mode of Cyanate and Azide Ions in $(py)_4M_4X_2MoS_4$ and $(phen)_2M_4X_2MoS_4$ ($M=Cu^I$ or Ag^I ; $X=OCN^-$ or N_3^-)

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Molybdenum complexes, $(py)_4M_4X_2MoS_4$ and $(phen)_2M_4X_2MoS_4$ ($M=Cu^I, Ag^I$; $X=OCN^-$ or N_3^-), have been synthesised and characterised by elemental analysis, molar conductance, magnetic moment, infrared and electronic spectral studies. End-to-end azide bridging for the azide complexes and oxygen-bonded cyanate terminals for the cyanate complexes have been proposed. The values of quantitative softness of metals ($E_m^\ddagger$) and ligands ($E_l^\ddagger$) have been found to support the proposed structure of the complexes.

The interactions of tetrathiomolybdates with trace elements like d^{10} transition metal ions, Cu^I or Ag^I , have been a subject of recent investigations and thereby studying complexes like M_3MoS_3Cl ($M=Cu^I$ or Ag^I)¹ and $L_4Cu_4X_2MoS_4$ ($L=py$ or pic ; $X=Cl^-$ or SCN^-)². These findings have created further interest in the study of $M-MoS_4^{2-}$ interactions. Recently, we have studied interactions of copper and silver acetylides with tetrathiomolybdate³. In the present communication we report the characterisation of $(L)_nM_4X_2MoS_4$ ($M=Cu^I$ or Ag^I ; $X=OCN^-$ or N_3^- ; $n=2$ when $L=phen$ and $n=4$ when $L=py$), a new family of $M-Mo-S$ system formed by the interaction of metal pseudohalide and ammonium tetrathiomolybdate in presence of ligands. This study may improve the chemical basis for interpreting the copper thiomolybdate interactions responsible, at least in part, for biological antagonism between copper and molyb-

denum which leads to copper deficiency particularly in ruminants.

Results and Discussion

Analytical data (Table 1) confirm the general formula, $L_nM_4X_2MoS_4$ ($M=Cu^I$ or Ag^I ; $X=OCN^-$ or N_3^- ; $n=2$ when $L=phen$ and $n=4$ when $L=py$) for these complexes. Molar conductance values of all the complexes in DMF were found in the range, 6.6–39.6 $\Omega^{-1} cm^2 mol^{-1}$ (Table 1) which indicate their non-conducting in nature. These are decomposed in the temperature range 220–305° and have low values of magnetic moments showing their diamagnetic character.

The electronic spectra of the complexes show the presence of four bands, out of which, two appear in the ranges 19 800–19 200 and 14 880–14 400

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPLEXES

Compd.	Colour	Decomp. temp. °C	Analysis % : Pound/(Calcd.)				Mol. cond. $\Omega^{-1} mol^{-1} cm^2$
			Mo	Cu/Ag	S	N	
$(py)_4Cu_4(OCN)_2MoS_4$	Violet	265	11.3 (10.9)	29.5 (28.9)	15.1 (14.6)	9.3 (9.6)	33.2
$(py)_4Ag_4(OCN)_2MoS_4$	Brown	305	8.9 (9.1)	40.3 (40.9)	11.9 (12.1)	7.8 (7.9)	39.6
$(phen)_2Cu_4(OCN)_2MoS_4$	Violet	250	10.5 (10.0)	26.0 (26.5)	13.3 (13.4)	7.3 (8.7)	6.6
$(phen)_2Ag_4(OCN)_2MoS_4$	Brown	285	9.6 (8.5)	37.7 (38.0)	10.9 (11.3)	7.0 (7.4)	22.0
$(py)_4Cu_4(N_3)_2MoS_4$	Violet	220	10.5 (10.9)	29.5 (28.9)	13.7 (14.6)	9.1 (9.6)	22.0
$(py)_4Ag_4(N_3)_2MoS_4$	Brown	280	8.8 (9.1)	40.2 (40.9)	12.4 (12.1)	7.6 (7.9)	13.2
$(phen)_2Cu_4(N_3)_2MoS_4$	Violet	260	10.5 (10.0)	26.0 (26.5)	13.0 (13.4)	7.4 (8.8)	15.4
$(phen)_2Ag_4(N_3)_2MoS_4$	Brown	290	8.9 (8.5)	40.2 (38.0)	10.9 (11.3)	7.1 (7.4)	30.8

TABLE 2—INFRARED SPECTRAL BAND (cm^{-1}) ASSIGNMENTS*

Compd.	$\nu_{\text{Mo-S}}(\text{br})$	$\nu_{\text{CN}}/\nu_{\text{asNNN}}$	$\nu_{\text{CO}}/\nu_{\text{sNNN}}$	$\delta_{\text{NCO}}/\delta_{\text{NNN}}$	$\nu_{\text{M-NNN}}$	$\nu_{\text{M-L}}$
(py) ₄ Cu ₄ (OCN) ₂ MoS ₄	450s	2 200m	1 340sh	642m	—	240w
(py) ₄ Ag ₄ (OCN) ₂ MoS ₄	445s	2 205m	1 345s	640w, 610m	—	250w
(phen) ₂ Cu ₄ (OCN) ₂ MoS ₄	445s	2 210s	1 345m	650m, 615m	—	245m
(phen) ₂ Ag ₄ (OCN) ₂ MoS ₄	445s	2 200w	1 350sh	640m, 610m	—	250w
(py) ₄ Cu ₄ (N ₃) ₂ MoS ₄	450m	2 095m	1 300w	618s	250m	235s
(py) ₄ Ag ₄ (N ₃) ₂ MoS ₄	430s	2 085m	1 305w, 1 312w	525s	220m, 275w	260s
(phen) ₂ Cu ₄ (N ₃) ₂ MoS ₄	445s	2 080m	1 310m	610sh	245w	250w
(phen) ₂ Ag ₄ (N ₃) ₂ MoS ₄	455s	2 080m	1 310w	615w	215m, 272w	250m

*br≡bridged, s≡strong, m≡medium, w≡weak, sh≡shoulder.

cm^{-1} , which may be assigned to the transitions, $t_{1g} \rightarrow 2e_g$ (ν_1) and $3t_{2g} \rightarrow 2e_g$ (ν_2) respectively. Other two bands at 10 000–9 600 and 8 920–8 400 cm^{-1} may be assigned to the transition, $t_{1g} \rightarrow 4t_{2g}$ (ν_3). The shifting of these bands from the positions reported for free MoS_4^{2-} ion indicates strong M– MoS_4^{2-} interaction.

In infrared spectra of the complexes, (py)₄M₄(OCN)₂MoS₄ and (phen)₂M₄(OCN)₂MoS₄ (M=Cu^I or Ag^I), a band observed at 450–445 cm^{-1} , indicates the presence of only bridged Mo–S groups^{3,4}. The positions of ν_{CN} , ν_{CO} and δ_{NCO} due to cyanate ion (Table 2) indicate the presence of terminal oxygen-bonded cyanate groups in these complexes⁵. The ligands show features of coordination through ring nitrogen as evidenced by the positive shift in the bands due to ring vibrations⁶. The positions of $\nu_{\text{M-L}}$ bands are found in the ranges prescribed for $\nu_{\text{Cu-L}}$ or $\nu_{\text{Ag-L}}$ modes⁷⁻⁹. On the basis of the above discussion following monomeric structures have been proposed for these complexes (Fig. 1).

The positions of ir bands due to $\nu_{\text{Mo-S}}$ at 450–430 cm^{-1} in the spectra of (py)₄M₄(N₃)₂MoS₄ and (phen)₂M₄(N₃)₂MoS₄ indicate the presence of only bridged Mo–S groups in these complexes^{3,4}. A band found at 2 095–2 060 cm^{-1} is assigned to $\nu_{\text{as}} \text{N}=\text{N}^+=\text{N}^-$ mode and another of medium intensity at 1 312–1 300 cm^{-1} is assigned to $\nu_s \text{N}=\text{N}^+=\text{N}^-$ mode. The third band found at 625–610 cm^{-1} is assigned to $\delta \text{N}=\text{N}^+=\text{N}^-$ mode. The positions of these bands resemble with those reported for end-to-end azide bridging^{7,10}. A band found at 275–215 cm^{-1} in the spectra of all the azide complexes is assigned to $\nu_{\text{M-N(N}_3)}$ mode^{7,8}.

The ligands py and phen, show features of coordination through ring nitrogen as evidenced by the positive shift in the bands due to ring vibrations⁶. Electronic spectral data as discussed earlier also indicate that sulphur atoms of tetrathiomolybdate are coordinated to Cu^I or Ag^I.

On the basis of the above studies the structures shown in Fig. 2 can be proposed for these complexes.

The proposed structures of the complexes can also be supported by quantitative softness values. The softness values of ligands ($E_m^\ddagger$) and metals ($E_n^\ddagger$)

Fig. 1

have been calculated by Klopman's equations^{11,12}. The results of these calculations are presented in Table 3. Ligand molecules in the complexes (py)₄M₄(OCN)₂MoS₄ and (phen)₂M₄(OCN)₂MoS₄, may coordinate to M in either fashion shown in structure X or Y (Fig. 3).

Fig. 2

$M_t = \text{Cu}^{\text{I}}$ or Ag^{I} bridged with sulphur of MoS_4^{2-} and L ; $M_b = \text{Cu}^{\text{I}}$ or Ag^{I} bridged with sulphur of MoS_4^{2-} and OCN^-

Fig. 3

ΔTE_n^* values were calculated by following a similar procedure as reported earlier¹¹. The $\Delta TE_n^*(M_b - M_t)$ values have been found higher

for structure (X) compared to those calculated for structure (Y) (Table 3) showing greater probability of structure (X) due to more stable M-S-Mo bridging.

In the complexes $(\text{py})_4\text{M}_4(\text{N}_3)_2\text{MoS}_4$ and $(\text{phen})_2\text{M}_4(\text{N}_3)_2\text{MoS}_4$, the ligand molecules have choice of coordination in either manner shown in structure (X') or (Y') (Fig. 4).

The $\Delta TE_n^*(M_b - M_t)$ values have been found higher for structure (X') compared to those calculated for (Y'), therefore, structure (X') is more probable.

TABLE 3 - SOFTNESS OF LIGANDS (E_m^*) AND METALS (E_n^*) AND TOTAL SOFTNESS DIFFERENCE VALUES [$\Delta TE_n^*(M - M')$] OF COMPLEXES*

Compd.	Structure [X]/[X']	Structure [Y]/[Y']
	$\Delta TE_n^*(M_b - M_t)$	$\Delta TE_n^*(M_b - M_t)$
$(\text{py})_4\text{Cu}_4(\text{OCN})_2\text{MoS}_4$	26.68	21.04
$(\text{py})_4\text{Ag}_4(\text{OCN})_2\text{MoS}_4$	26.68	21.04
$(\text{phen})_2\text{Cu}_4(\text{OCN})_2\text{MoS}_4$	27.24	21.04
$(\text{phen})_2\text{Ag}_4(\text{OCN})_2\text{MoS}_4$	27.24	21.04
$(\text{py})_4\text{Cu}_4(\text{N}_3)_2\text{MoS}_4$	55.3	7.58
$(\text{py})_4\text{Ag}_4(\text{N}_3)_2\text{MoS}_4$	55.3	7.58
$(\text{phen})_2\text{Cu}_4(\text{N}_3)_2\text{MoS}_4$	55.86	7.58
$(\text{phen})_2\text{Ag}_4(\text{N}_3)_2\text{MoS}_4$	55.86	7.58

$E_n^* \text{Cu}^{\text{I}} = -2.33$, $E_n^* \text{Ag}^{\text{I}} = -2.84$; $E_m^*(\text{MoS}_4^{2-}) = 7.58$.
 $E_m^*(\text{OCN}^-) = -10.52$, $E_m^*(\text{N}_3) = -9.67$, $E_m^*(\text{py}) = -11.93$;
 $E_m^*(\text{phen}) = -12.07$. M_b and $M_t = \text{Cu}^{\text{I}}$ or Ag^{I} .

*Softness values of metal ions and ligands calculated in DMSO medium.

Experimental

Reagent grade solvent were used after purification by standard methods. Pyridine (Glaxo), 1,10-phenanthroline (E. Merck), copper(I) chloride (S. Merck), sodium metabisulphite (S. Merck), ammonium heptamolybdate (Loba) and silver nitrate (E. Merck) were used as such. Potassium cyanate (Riedel) and sodium azide (Loba) were also used as such. $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{MoS}_4$ was prepared by the method described earlier⁸.

M_t = Cu^I or Ag^I bridged with N of azide and L; M_b = Cu^I or Ag^I bridged with other end of azide and sulphur of MoS₄²⁻

Fig. 4

Silver(I) azide (AgN₃): An aqueous solution (40 ml) of NaN₃ (0.65 g, 10 mmol) was treated with aqueous solution (40 ml) of AgNO₃ (1.7 g, 10 mmol). The white precipitate formed was washed with water followed by alcohol and ether and dried in a vacuum oven over anhydrous H₂SO₄. The analytical results gave empirical formula AgN₃, yield 83%.

Silver(I) cyanate (AgNCO): It was prepared by treating an aqueous solution (40 ml) of KCNO (0.81 g, 10 mmol) with an aqueous solution of AgNO₃ (1.7 g, 10 mmol). The white precipitate formed was washed with water followed by ether and dried under reduced pressure. The analytical results gave empirical formula AgNCO, yield 85%.

(py)₄Cu₄(OCN)₂MoS₄ and (py)₄Cu₄(N₃)₂MoS₄: To a suspension of cuprous chloride (0.39 g, 4 mmol) in DMSO (15 ml), a solution of KCNO (0.26 g, 1 mmol) in ethanol (10 ml) was added and stirred for 1 h. Pyridine (0.32 ml, 4 mmol) was then added to it and further stirred for about 5 h to get a deep red solution containing some insoluble matter. The insoluble matter was removed by filtration which on washing with DMSO and weighing after drying was proved to be a mixture of KCl and NH₄Cl on chemical tests. The filtrate was left for a weak at room temperature and the resulting deep violet crystals were washed with DMSO followed by ether and dried in a vacuum oven: (py)₄Cu₄(OCN)₂MoS₄ (60%); (py)₄Cu₄(N₃)₂MoS₄ was prepared in a similar manner by using NaN₃ instead of KCNO, yield 65%.

(phen)₂Cu₄(OCN)₂MoS₄ and (phen)₂Cu₄(N₃)₂MoS₄: To the suspension of cuprous chloride (0.39 g, 4 mmol) in DMSO, solutions of (NH₄)₂MoS₄ (0.26 g, 1 mmol) in DMSO (15 ml), KCNO (0.32 g, 4 mmol) in ethanol (10 ml) and 1,10-phenanthroline (0.40 g, 4 mmol) in DMSO (10 ml) were added and the mixture was stirred for about 5 h. The precipitated potassium chloride and ammonium chloride were discarded. The filtrate was kept for a weak

at room temperature and the resulting violet crystals were washed with DMSO followed by ether and dried under reduced pressure: (phen)₂Cu₄(OCN)₂MoS₄, yield 53%. (phen)₂Cu₄(N₃)₂MoS₄ was prepared in a similar manner using NaN₃ in the place of KCNO, yield 67%.

(py)₄Ag₄(OCN)₂MoS₄ and (py)₄Ag₄(N₃)₂MoS₄: To a suspension of AgOCN (0.60 g, 4 mmol) in DMSO (50 ml), pyridine (0.32 ml, 4 mmol) and (NH₄)₂MoS₄ (0.26 g, 1 mmol) in DMSO (15 ml) were added and the mixture was stirred for about 12 h at room temperature. The precipitated potassium chloride and ammonium chloride were discarded. The filtrate was treated with diethyl ether (5 ml) and left overnight, and the resulting brownish solid was washed with DMSO followed by ether and dried in a vacuum oven at 70°: (py)₄Ag₄(OCN)₂MoS₄, yield 67%. (py)₄Ag₄(N₃)₂MoS₄ was prepared similarly by using AgN₃ in place of AgOCN, yield 60%.

(phen)₂Ag₄(OCN)₂MoS₄ and (phen)₂Ag₄(N₃)₂MoS₄: To a suspension of AgOCN (0.60 g, 4 mmol) in DMSO (50 ml), solutions of phenanthroline (0.40 g, 2 mmol) in DMSO (10 ml) and (NH₄)₂MoS₄ (0.26 g, 1 mmol) in DMSO (15 ml) were added and the mixture was stirred for about 12 h at room temperature. The precipitated potassium chloride and ammonium chloride were discarded. The filtrate was treated with diethyl ether (5 ml) and on standing overnight a brownish solid was formed which was washed with DMSO followed by ether and dried under reduced pressure: (phen)₂Ag₄(OCN)₂MoS₄, yield 50%. (phen)₂Ag₄(N₃)₂MoS₄ was prepared similarly by using AgN₃ instead of AgOCN, yield 54%.

Molybdenum was estimated as lead molybdate, copper as cuprous thiocyanate, silver as silver(I) chloride and sulphur as barium sulphate using standard methods¹³.

Infrared spectra (nujol) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer and electronic spectra (nujol) on a Cary-14 spectrophotometer. Mag-

netic susceptibility was measured made by Gouy's method using $\text{Hg}[\text{Co}(\text{NCS})_4]$ as standard. Molar conductance was determined in DMF at 0.001 M dilution using an Elico CM-82T conductivity bridge.

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